

THE FLOATING BRIDGE: ASSESSING THE POLITICS OF PENSION AND GRATUITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Pension in Nigeria has been very problematic and has provoked a lot of researches. Workers work and retire in good health and suddenly drifted into ailment and abject penury due to non-payment of gratuity and epileptic pension payment. Therefore, this study investigated different pension regimes in Nigeria and their inability to address the plight of the retirees. The study adopted qualitative research methodology and content analysis technique was used as medium of analysis. After interrogating the nuances of pension in Nigeria, some revelations were made and based on the revelations, the study concludes that: Government should mount awareness campaign drive by in print, electronic and social media. Scale up micro pension in the informal sector. Government should prudently manage the pension fund to ensure that retirees receive their monthly pension instantly at retirement and to reorganize PenCom, PFAs and PFCs, and also organize regular workshops and seminars for the pension agencies and stakeholder.*

1. Introduction

Pension is a kind of annuity for the retired public servants for life (in some cases also for his dependents after his death) Pension is paid in fixed monthly amounts –oftentimes a certain percentage of the salary. From the government point of view the pension is given in recognition of long and meritorious service. The pension system, unless specially adopted to meet the hardship of the time, results in hardship to the family of a white- or blue-collar worker who dies prematurely in service, or on the verge of

retirement or before enjoying the pensionary benefit for any appreciable period (Abah, 1997). Pensions do not involve any risk or trouble to the employee after retirement.

The Pension Ordinance of 1951 was the first ever legislative Act on pension in the public sector in Nigeria. Nine years later (that is in 1961), the National Provident Fund (NPF) was established to address pension issues in the private sector. This was followed by the Pension Act No.102 of 1979 and the Armed Forces Pension Act No.103 of 1979. In 1987, the police and other

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government agencies pension scheme was established under Pension Act No.75 of 1987; in the same year, Local Government Staff Pension Board (LGSPB) was established to cater for pension matters among local government employees (Sule & Ezugwu, 2006). However, in the private sector, pension reforms were slow and marginal since 1961. It was only in 1993 that a pragmatic step was made by government to address the many problems of pension in the private sector. In this regard, government established the National Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF) in 1993, to cater for pension issues in the private sector.

The general characteristics of the Nigerian Pension Scheme before 2004 reform were noncontributory and bedeviled by many impediments. The large number of pensioners and mismanagement of pension funds impose heavy burden on government and the private sector. According to Chukwuemeka (2021), the public pension debt as in 2023 was over four trillion naira. The cumulative effect of the debt is that, government was unable to service pensions of retirees, as a result, pensioners could not pay children school fees, cater for their health and other necessities of life.

This precarious situation necessitated the enactment of the Pension Reform Act of 2004. The 2004 Pension Reform Act is a paradigm shift from the 1979 Pension Act. Under the new scheme, employers and employees alike are to

contribute 7.5 percent of employees' monthly emolument which include basic salary, housing and transport allowance. However, military personnel are to contribute 2.5 percent while the Federal Government contributes 12.5 percent of the employees' monthly emolument (Pension Reform Act, 2004). The scheme covers the private sector with

Five or more employees. The only exceptions are public employees who have three years or less to retire with effect from the date of enactment of the Pension Act being 30th June 2004 (National Pension Commission, 2004). The employer may elect under the 2004 Pension Act to bear the full burden of the pension by contributing not less than 15 percent of the employees' monthly emolument.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The study investigates the rationale for pension in Nigeria and also to determine if implementation of pension regimes in Nigeria is effective and efficient. To proffer solutions to the identified problems.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Interrogating the new Pension Act of 2004 in Nigeria

The objective of the new pension scheme, which is contributory pension scheme, include among others to ensure that every employee in the private and public sectors receives his/her benefits as and when due; to establish a uniform rules, regulations, standards and laws for the

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administration, management and payment of pension funds in the country. The scheme was also established to assist employees by ensuring that they save to cater for life after retirement. More so, the scheme was to address the huge unsustainable pension deficit estimated at about two trillion naira which characterized the former (Ugochukwu, 2020).

2.2 Provisions of the Pension Act of 2004:

(1) All government agencies and private organizations operating anywhere in Nigeria and employing five or more staff must ensure that all its employees have pensions.

(2) The penalty for non-compliance includes a 2% per month charge of un-remitted amount as long as the fault persists.

(3) The pension funds must be managed by a Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) licensed by the National Pension Commission and the funds must be deposited with a Pension Fund Custodian (PFC) licenced by the National Pension Commission.

(4) Contribution by employees is 7.5% of their monthly emoluments comprising basic salary, housing and transport allowance to be matched by employer's contribution of 7.5% every month. This brings it to a total of 15% every month. In case of military personnel, the contribution per employee is 2.5% while the employer's contribution is 12.5%.

Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) Pension Scheme. According to Aminu (2004), the contributory

pension scheme would address the pension deficit of the past in Nigeria; that the scheme as of July, 2010, has an asset of 1.7 trillion naira (11.3 billion dollars) across the country.

The contributory pension scheme is expected to have multiplier effect on workers attitude towards retirement, commitment to duty, and labor retention as well as attitude towards corruption especially in the civil or public service. This is because the uncertainty of receiving pension and gratuity after retirement was largely responsible for high labor turnover in the civil service. WHO (2007), posits that, poor remuneration, delay in payment of fringe benefits and poor conditions of service among others are jointly responsible for the exodus of medical personnel from Nigeria to the United States of America and the United Kingdom.

2.3 The politics of pension in Nigeria

Worker's commitment to organizational goals has received wide attention by scholars (Steer, 1977). Worker's commitment here entails the level of job involvement (Lodahl & Kejners, 1965). It includes internal work motivation (Osisoma and Chukwuemeka, 2020) and the willingness of an employee to invest personal effort for the sake of the organization (Agba, Nkpoyen & Ushie, 2010). It involves attitudes or orientation towards organizational goals or objectives (Osuagwu, Chukwuemeka and Nchedo 2021). Commitment is positive and consistent attitude towards organizational goal

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that are produced by exchange consideration. Worker's commitment is a function of many variables including, characteristics of job situation, the work environment, leadership style and career development (Salanick, 1977; Agba, Nkoyen & Ushie, 2010; Ushie, Agba, Agba & Chime, 2010; Ushie, Agba, Agba & Best, 2010). Employees' commitment could also be influenced by the level of job involvement or the responsibilities of the worker (Dike 2006).

Commitment is also tied to how well an employee is motivated. Motivation here entails the process of influencing employees' behavior towards the attainment of organizational goal (Chukwuemeka, 2013). Motivation includes meeting the psychological, financial and emotional needs of workers. Pension is part of motivation and could help attain the psychological and emotional needs of workers, because it assures them of life after retirement.

A good pension scheme could determine the level of workers commitment as well as influence whether an employee will do his/her work properly. According to Sule & Ezugwu (2009), good pension guarantees employee's comfort and commitment to the organization during his/her active years.

The absence of good pension scheme in the past was largely responsible for the psychological, physiological and economic problems among retirees in Nigeria. It is expected that retirees receive certain benefits such as gratuity and

pension. Gratuity here is the worker's entitlement as soon as he/she makes exit from active service; while pension is the regular payment to a retiree until his or her last days on earth. Most often gratuities and pension are not paid as and when due; consequently, retirees cannot afford school fees for their children, pay house rents or take care of other necessities of life (Chukwuemeka, 2013).

The provoking thought of facing life after retirement creates psychological and emotional abnormally among workers especially those who are approaching retirement age (Nwizu , 2002). While retirement remains luxury in developed countries in Nigeria workers are always afraid of financial insecurity after retirement. The social insecurity makes retirement unattractive to workers in Nigeria (Chukwuemeka, 2013). Workers who are in the payroll of government cannot fend for themselves, not to talk of when they are retired.

The fear of uncertainty after retirement is also responsible for age falsification among civil servants in Nigeria. Retirement in Nigeria also goes with social isolation and poverty; consequently, retirees even at very old age look for employment or jobs to maintain themselves. This scenario shows that the meager amount received by pensioners before the introduction of the contributory pension scheme was grossly inadequate to sustain a retiree and his/her family.

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In the public service across the globe, it has been the duty of every government to make some provision for public servants when they retire, either by the grant of some kind of the life annuity (pension) or by payment of a lump sum in the shape of provident fund, gratuity etc.

If the retiring public servants are not provided with the retirement benefits, that would mean either the public officers would have to be retained in service for life in which case there would be congestion in the service; the service would be overburdened with old and inefficient men popularly referred to as 'dead wood', or if retirement is insisted on, many of the ex-employees would have to live in want and destitution (Nwizu, 2002). This would make government work unpopular and reduce the attraction of public service and the dignity of the state as an employer. It would also affect adversely the morale of those still in service. Bribery and corruption may creep into the service because of an anxiety for the future. That could also make some unscrupulous public servants intermittently swear frivolous affidavits to bring their age down to enable them continue in service. Experience has shown that many die while in office which is referred to as 'died in active service'.

It is imperative to understand that retirement benefits are not optional grant to an employee who have served his father land for sixty or sixty-

five years of age. It rather represents the following:

- (a) The benevolence of the state towards its old employees as a reward for past good services
- (b) Is a part of the social security?
- (c) Is simply a deferred pay to which employees are entitled as a matter of right.

2.4 Types of pensions

Pension can be classified as contributory and non-contributory pensions. A pension scheme is said to be contributory when both the government and the employee contribute (not necessarily equally) towards its payment. It is noncontributory if the whole amount for its payment is funded by the government or the employer only. There is not much of difference between the two, financially speaking, for if the pension system is non-contributory, the salaries will be proportionately lower and vice versa. Employee's contribution creates a sort of right for him to pensions, and he may claim a voice in the management of the scheme.

2.5 The Erstwhile pension schemes we had in the public service before the Pension Act of 2004

- (1) Retiring pension – granted to an officer who is permitted to retire after completing a fixed period of qualifying service, usually 30-35 years.
- (2) Compensatory pension: granted to an officer whose permanent post is abolished, and government is unable to provide him with suitable alternative employment.

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(3) Superannuation pension – given to an officer who retires at the prescribed age

i.e 60-65 years as the case may be.

(4) Compassionate allowances: when pension is not admissible on account of a public servant's removal from service for misconduct, insolvency, or inefficiency.

Gratuity or Provident fund:

This is a lump sum payment to the public officer on retirement to the accumulation of which he has contributed. The provident fund accumulations are subject to variation with fluctuations in the prevailing rate of interest. When the interest rate is high, it leads to the relative financial advantage of provident fund.

Retirement in Nigeria: The need for retirement:

Public officers cannot work effectively and efficiently old age; as a result, they remain active and productive up to a certain age after which they need rest. In Nigeria as well as other countries of the world, employees of the government as a result of old age have to retire on reaching the prescribed age of superannuation. This is done both in the interest of the workers and efficiency of the service and the health of the public officers. Retirement is needed to provide promotional opportunities in the service. Old employees are retired to make room for the promotion of the young men in the service to the higher posts and the recruitment of

persons from outside to fill up the vacancies thus created.

Retirement Age:

In Nigeria, the prescribed age of superannuation or retirement varies from 60. 5 years. This varies from country according to the climatic conditions and life expectancy. In the United States of America, it is 65 to 70 years, in Britain 60 to 65 years, and India 55 in case of non-ministerial and 60 in case of ministerial services (expected in case of those not in service on 31st March, 1938 for whom it is 55) (Nwizu, 2002). In Britain there is an optional age of retirement and compulsory one at 60 and 65 years respectively. At 60, an employee has the option to retire on the usual pensionary rights if he so chooses and the Government also has the option to make him retire if it thinks it fit in the interest of efficiency byut at 65 he must compulsorily retire. Since World War II, retirement at 50 in case of incapacity has also been allowed.

Rules guiding retirement and pension benefits:

Retirement benefits may be agreed at 3 times or 2 times the terminal salary of a retiring staff. This is the benefit given to such staff in a golden handshake to say 'thank you for having served us so well'. Pensions on the other hand are lifelong benefits, which the staff derives from their employments after they have attained certain ages sometimes 60, sometimes 65 years. Then they are placed on 22/3 of their terminal salary

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for the rest of their life. Some workers such as generals in the army retire on full general's salary and the full perquisites of office (e.g., if he had an ADC he retains him, if he had stewards, irregular rations of food, meat, etc he retains same).

Gratuity in a non-pensionable job (Contract Employment):

Employment in a non-pensionable job is popularly referred to as 'contract employment'. The normal employment process in the public service is followed which include the salary structure of public service. Contract employment is subject to renewal – it could be yearly, quarterly period as may be agreed in the contract paper. In the course of incapacitation, old age or poor health conditions, the contract employee is not entitled to any benefits. In most cases contract employees are not entitled to leave or leave grants. Certain percentage of the total basic salary is paid as contract addition which is in lieu of gratuity and pension. In some cases, 15% of the basis salary is paid to the contract employee as contract addition.

2.6 Pitfalls of Contributory Pension in Nigeria; Pension Act of 2004 in focus

Major challenges of the current contributory pension scheme include the issue of accrued rights, incessant exit agitations and pension liabilities. It would be recalled that when Nigeria transitioned from the defined benefit (DB) scheme to the CPS, one major issue was accrued pension rights.

The Nigerian government has struggled with consistent and adequate funding for accrued rights under the defined pension scheme. Budgetary allocations often fall short of the required amounts, leading to delays in disbursement. The lack of a clear plan for paying off this deficit has exacerbated the issue.

Pension Fund Commission of Nigeria (PenCom), Pension Fund Administrators and Pension Fund Custodians (PFCs) also have teething challenges. Pension fund Administrators (PFAs) and the National Pension Commission (PenCom) have highlighted the challenges they have faced in their efforts to smoothly push the federal government micro pension plan initiative to the targeted market. However, in the mist of the challenges, increased public awareness and review of the guidelines among others is the way to go. Osuagwu, Chukwuemeka and Nchedo (2021) contend that the challenges were of two folds from the informal sector workers and PFAs. From the informal sector workers, they highlighted the challenges as lack of awareness, mistrust about the pension system, absence of appropriate incentives such as collateral for, micro finance and lack of financial literacy.

From the PFAs they pointed out the challenges as short-term perspectives base of the micro pension plan and perceived associated costs, inadequate awareness campaigns, slow adoption of shared services arrangements by pension fund operators, poor service delivery, weak economic

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indices occasioned by inflation as well as increased poverty levels. Osuagwu, Chukwuemeka and Nchedo, 2021) further argue that the pension agents in Nigeria have impacted negatively on the implementation efforts both the pension fund administrators and PenCom. The PenCom claimed that some efforts have been made to push the micro pension scheme to the targeted market as collaborations and stakeholders' engagements through engineering leaderships of associated unions cooperatives, civil society organizations and the media.

Other challenges include:

(a) Inability of the PFCs to account for the money deposited in their banks and ensure quick release when demanded

(b) Inability of PenCom to institute a framework to capture retirees few months before retirement to ensure that all the paper work is completed before an employee retires.

(c) The Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) inability to keep accurate and up to date records of employees under their umbrella.

(d) the issue of transition from one PFA to another, e.g. when Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) floated her own Pension Fund Administrator (NUPEMCO) , many teaching staff in the universities transited from their erstwhile PFAs to NUPEMCO.

(e) Government insincerity to manage pension funds in custody of PFCs. Last few years, it was

observed that the Government borrowed chunk of money from the pension funds which they are yet to repay.

3. Methodology|

The study was quantitative in nature. Therefore, relevant literature was reviewed and discussion was centered on analyzing contents.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Most Nigerian workers dread retirement because they are not sure that when they retire, they are going to receive their pension contribution. This has given rise to many employees falsifying their age in order to remain in service as long as possible. Most workers who have taken the courage to retire when they are due to retire scarcely live up to four years because of poverty and hardship associated with inability to receive their gratuity and pension.

Thus, the following need to be done to assuage the quagmire associated with the new contributory pension scheme in Nigeria:

(a) Mount awareness campaign drive by in print, electronic and social media

(b) Scale up micro pension in the informal sector

(c) Prudently manage the pension fund to ensure that retirees receive their monthly pension instantly at retirement

(d) Reorganise PenCom, PFAs and PFCs, and also organize regular workshops and seminars for the pension agents and stakeholder.

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